

**International Journal Of Software Engineering &
Applications (IJSEA)**

(ERA Listed)

ISSN : 0975 - 9018 (Online); 0976-2221 (Print)

<http://www.airccse.org/journal/ijsea/ijsea.html>

**Current Issue: November 2018, Volume
10, Number 6 --- Table of Contents**

<http://www.airccse.org/journal/ijsea/current.html>

A FORMAL METHOD FOR MAPPING SOFTWARE ENGINEERING PRACTICES TO ESSENCE

Murat Pasa Uysal

Department of Management Information Systems, Başkent University, Ankara,
Turkey

ABSTRACT

Essence Framework (EF) aims at addressing the core problems of software engineering (SE) and its practices. As a relatively new framework, one important issue for EF has been mapping software practices to its conceptual domain. Although there are several works describing systematic procedures, a review of literature cannot suggest a study using a formal method. The study is conducted according to the guidelines of Design Science Research (DSR) Method. The research contribution is classified as an “application of a new solution (the formal method) to a new problem (mapping software practices to EF). The formal method employs an algorithm based on Concept Algebra and it is applied in a Scrum case study. The results are promising and they differ from the ones exist in the current EF related literature.

KEYWORDS

Software Engineering Practice, Essence Framework, Formal Method, Concept Algebra

For More Details: <http://airconline.com/ijsea/V9N6/9618ijsea01.pdf>

Volume Link: <http://www.airccse.org/journal/ijsea/current.html>

REFERENCES

- [1] Park S., Jacobson I., Myburgh B., Johnson P. and McMahon P.E. 2014. SEMAT yesterday, today and tomorrow, SEMAT, retrieved from <http://semat.org>.
- [2] OMG 2016. SMSC/15-12-02 [Essence–Kernel and Language for Software Engineering Methods, Specification](#) v.1.1.
- [3] Park J.S., McMahon P.E. and Myburgh B. 2016. Scrum powered by Essence. ACM SIGSOFT Software Engineering Notes. 1-8, 41(1).
- [4] Park J.S. 2015. Essence- Powered Scrum: A generic approach to describing practices using essence kernel and language, retrieved from http://old.semat.org/wp_content/uploads/2015/03/1-EssencePowered-Scrum-June.pdf,
- [5] Giray G., Tüzün E., Tekinerdoğan B. and Macit Y. 2016. [Systematic approach for mapping software development methods to the Essence Framework](#). In Proceedings of 5th International Workshop on Theory-Oriented Software Engineering, Austin, TX, USA, May 16 2016.
- [6] Sedano T., P´eraire C. and Lohn J. 2015. [Towards generating Essence Kernels using Genetic Algorithms](#). In Proceedings of International Conference on Soft Computing and Software Engineering (Berkeley, California, USA, March 5-6, 2015).
- [7] Uysal M.P. and Giray G 2017. [An Essence Framework approach to software engineering research](#). In Proceedings of 11th. National Software Engineering Symposium(Alanya, Antalya, Turkey, September 18-20, 2017).
- [8] Wang Y. 2008. On Concept Algebra: [A denotational mathematical structure for knowledge and software modeling](#). Int. Journal of Cognitive Informatics and Natural Intelligence, 2(2), 1-19.
- [9] Rubin K.S. 2013. Essential Scrum: A practical guide to the most popular agile process. Addison Wesley, NY, USA.
- [10] Schwaber K. and Sutherland J. 2017. The Scrum Guide: The definitive guide to Scrum: The rules of the game. Creative Commons, USA.
- [11] Vaishnavi, V.K., Kuechler W.J. 2008. [Design Science Research methods and patterns: Innovating information and communication technology](#), USA, Auerbach Publications, Taylor & Francis Group.
- [12] Gregor S., Hevner A.R., 2013. [Positioning and presenting design science research for maximum impact, MIS Quarterly](#), 37(2), pp.337-355.

AUTHOR

Assoc. Prof. Dr. Murat Pasa Uysal, is at the Department of Management Information Systems in Baskent University. He holds a B.S degree in electrical & electronic engineering, a M.S degree in computer engineering, and a Ph.D. degree in educational technology. He completed his post-doctoral studies at Rochester Institute of Technology in New York, which was on software re-engineering and Information Technologies (IT) Governance. He served as an advisor and engineer for different types of IT projects in Turkish Army (TA) for many years, and conducted studies addressing the problems of TA in the research areas of IT. He has been teaching IT, information systems and software engineering related courses. His research interest is also in the areas of software engineering, information systems (IS), instructional methods and tools for computer programming and IS

A NOVEL EFFORT ESTIMATION MODEL FOR SOFTWARE REQUIREMENT CHANGES DURING SOFTWARE DEVELOPMENT PHASE

Jalal Shah, Nazri Kama and Nur Azaliah A Bakar

**Department of Razak Faculty of Technology and Informatics, Universiti Teknologi
Malaysia, Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia**

ABSTRACT

Software Requirements Changes is a typical phenomenon in any software development project. Restricting incoming changes might cause user dissatisfaction and allowing too many changes might cause delay in project delivery. Moreover, the acceptance or rejection of the change requests become challenging for software project managers when these changes are occurred in Software Development Phase. Where in Software Development Phase software artifacts are not in consistent state such as: some of the class artifacts are Fully Developed, some are Half Developed, some are Major Developed, some are Minor Developed and some are Not Developed yet. However, software effort estimation and change impact analysis are the two most common techniques which might help software project managers in accepting or rejecting change requests during Software Development Phase. The aim of this research is to develop a new software change effort estimation model which helps software project manager in estimating the effort for software Requirement Changes during Software Development Phase. Thus, this research has analyzed the existing effort estimation models and change impact analysis techniques for Software Development Phase from the literature and proposed a new software change effort estimation model by combining change impact analysis technique with effort estimation model. Later, the new proposed model has been evaluated by selecting four small size software projects as case selections in applying experimental approach. The experiment results show that the overall Mean Magnitude Relative Error value produced by the new proposed model is under 25%. Hence it is concluded that the new proposed model is applicable in estimating the amount of effort for requirement changes during SDP

KEYWORDS

Software Change Effort Estimation, Software Requirement Changes, Function Point Analysis, Constructive.Cost Model and Software Development Phase.

For More Details: <http://airconline.com/ijsea/V9N6/9618ijsea02.pdf>

Volume Link: <http://www.airccse.org/journal/ijsea/current.html>

REFERENCES

- [1] H. Kerzner, Project management best practices: Achieving global excellence: John Wiley & Sons, 2018.
- [2] M. Gupta and A. Kalia, "[Empirical Study of Software Metrics](#)," Research Journal of Science and Technology, vol. 9, pp. 17-24, 2017.
- [3] T. O. A. Lehtinen, M. V. Mäntylä, J. Vanhanen, J. Itkonen, and C. Lassenius, "[Perceived causes of software project failures – An analysis of their relationships](#)," Information and Software Technology, vol. 56, pp. 623-643, 6// 2014.
- [4] R. Kaur and J. Sengupta, "[Software Process Models and Analysis on Failure of Software Development Projects](#)," CoRR, vol. abs/1306.1068, 2013.
- [5] M. Bano, S. Imtiaz, N. Ikram, M. Niazi, and M. Usman, "[Causes of requirement change - A systematic literature review](#)," in Evaluation & Assessment in Software Engineering (EASE 2012), 16th International Conference on, 2012, pp. 22-31.
- [6] J. Shah and N. Kama, "[Issues of Using Function Point Analysis Method for Requirement Changes During Software Development Phase.](#)," presented at the Asia Pacific Requirements Engineering Conference, Melaka Malaysia, 2018.
- [7] J. Shah and N. Kama, "[Extending Function Point Analysis Effort Estimation Method for Software Development Phase](#)," presented at the Proceedings of the 2018 7th International Conference on Software and Computer Applications, Kuantan, Malaysia, 2018.
- [8] J. Shah and N. Kama, "[Extending Function Point Analysis Effort Estimation Method for Software Development Phase](#)," in Proceedings of the 2018 7th International Conference on Software and Computer Applications, 2018, pp. 77-81.
- [9] Kama and M. Halmi, "[Extending Change Impact Analysis Approach for Change Effort Estimation in the Software Development Phase](#)," in WSEAS International Conference. Proceedings. Recent Advances in Computer Engineering Series, 2013.
- [10] N. K. Jalal Shah, Saiful Adli Ismail, "[An Empirical Study with Function Point Analysis for Software Development Phase Method](#)," presented at the 2018 7th International Conference on Software and Information Engineering (ICSIE 2018), Cairo, Egypt, 2018.
- [11] D. Kchaou, N. Bouassida, and H. Ben-Abdallah, "[Change effort estimation based on UML diagrams application in UCP and COCOMOII](#)," in 2015 10th International Joint Conference on Software Technologies (ICSOFT), 2015, pp. 1-8.

- [12] D. Kchaou, N. Bouassida, and H. Ben-Abdallah, "[UML models change impact analysis using a text similarity technique.](#)" IET Software, vol. 11, pp. 27-37, 2017.
- [13] A. Hira, S. Sharma, and B. Boehm, "c," presented at the Proceedings of the International Conference on Software and Systems Process, Austin, Texas, 2016.
- [14] A. Hira and B. Boehm, "[Function Point Analysis for Software Maintenance.](#)" presented at the Proceedings of the 10th ACM/IEEE International Symposium on Empirical Software Engineering and Measurement, Ciudad Real, Spain, 2016.
- [15] L. M. Alves, A. Sousa, P. Ribeiro, and R. J. Machado, "[An empirical study on the estimation of software development effort with use case points.](#)" in 2013 IEEE Frontiers in Education Conference (FIE), 2013, pp. 101-107.
- [16] H. Rastogi, S. Dhankhar, and M. Kakkar, "[A survey on software effort estimation techniques.](#)" in Confluence The Next Generation Information Technology Summit(Confluence), 2014 5th International Conference -, 2014, pp. 826-830.
- [17] K. Usharani, V. V. Ananth, and D. Velmurugan, "[A survey on software effort estimation.](#)" in 2016 International Conference on Electrical, Electronics, and Optimization Techniques (ICEEOT), 2016, pp. 505-509.
- [18] R. Britto, V. Freitas, E. Mendes, and M. Usman, "[Effort Estimation in Global Software Development: A Systematic Literature Review.](#)" in 2014 IEEE 9th International Conference on Global Software Engineering, 2014, pp. 135-144.
- [19] A. Idri, M. Hosni, and A. Abran, "[Systematic literature review of ensemble effort estimation.](#)" Journal of Systems and Software, vol. 118, pp. 151-175, 8// 2016.
- [20] M. d. F. Junior, M. Fantinato, and V. Sun, "[Improvements to the Function Point Analysis Method: A Systematic Literature Review.](#)" IEEE Transactions on Engineering Management, vol. 62, pp. 495-506, 2015.
- [21] B.Chinthanet, P.Phannachitta, Y. Kamei, P. Leelaprute, A. Rungsawang, N. Ubayashi, et al., "[A review and comparison of methods for determining the best analogies in analogy-based software effort estimation.](#)" presented at the Proceedings of the 31st Annual ACM Symposium on Applied Computing, Pisa, Italy, 2016.
- [22] S.Basri, N.Kama, F. Haneem, and S. A. Ismail, "[Predicting effort for requirement changes during software development.](#)" presented at the Proceedings of the Seventh Symposium on Information and Communication Technology, Ho Chi Minh City, Viet Nam, 2016.
- [23] M.Shahid and S.Ibrahim, "[Change impact analysis with a software traceability approach to support software maintenance.](#)" in 2016 13th International Bhurban Conference on Applied Sciences and Technology (IBCAST), 2016, pp. 391-396.
- [24] S.Basri, N.Kama, and R. Ibrahim, "[A Novel Effort Estimation Approach for Requirement Changes during Software Development Phase.](#)" International Journal of Software Engineering and Its Applications, vol. 9, pp. 237-252, 2015.

- [25] O.Fedotova, L.Teixeira, and H. Alvelos, "[Software Effort Estimation with Multiple Linear Regression: Review and Practical Application](#)," J. Inf. Sci. Eng., vol. 29, pp. 925-945, 2013.
- [26] A.Idri, F.a. Amazal, and A. Abran, "[Analogy-based software development effort estimation: A systematic mapping and review](#)," Information and Software Technology, vol. 58, pp. 206-230, 2// 2015.
- [27] M.Kaur and S.K. Sehra, "[Particle swarm optimization based effort estimation using Function Point analysis](#)," in Issues and Challenges in Intelligent Computing Techniques (ICICT), 2014 International Conference on, 2014, pp. 140-145.
- [28] N.K. b. Jalal Shah*a, Amelia Zahari, "[AN EMPIRICAL STUDY WITH FUNCTION POINT ANALYSIS FOR REQUIREMENT CHANGES DURING SOFTWARE DEVELOPMENT PHASE](#)," in ASIA International Multidisciplinary Conference 2017, Johor Bharu, 2017.
- [29] B.Sufyan, K. Nazri, H. Faizura, and A. I. Saiful, "[Predicting effort for requirement changes during software development](#)," presented at the Proceedings of the Seventh Symposium on Information and Communication Technology, Ho Chi Minh City, Viet Nam, 2016.
- [30] V.K. Bardsiri, D.N.A. Jawawi, A. K. Bardsiri, and E. Khatibi, "[LMES: A localized multi-estimator model to estimate software development effort](#)," Engineering Applications of Artificial Intelligence, 2013.
- [31] F.Ferrucci, C. Gravino, and L. Lavazza, "[Simple function points for effort estimation: a further assessment](#)," presented at the Proceedings of the 31st Annual ACM Symposium on Applied Computing, Pisa, Italy, 2016.
- [32] A.J. Albrecht, "[AD/M productivity measurement and estimate validation](#)," IBM Corporate Information Systems, IBM Corp., Purchase, NY, 1984.
- [33] P.Vickers and C. Street, "[An Introduction to Function Point Analysis](#)," School of Computing and Mathematical Sciences, Liverpool John Moores University, Liverpool, UK, 2001.
- [34] S.Sabrjoo, M Khalili, and M. Nazari, "[Comparison of the accuracy of effort estimation methods](#)," in 2015 2nd International Conference on Knowledge-Based Engineering and Innovation (KBEL), 2015, pp. 724-728.
- [35] V.Anandhi and R. M. Chezian, "[Regression techniques in software effort estimation using cocomo dataset](#)," in Intelligent Computing Applications (ICICA), 2014 International Conference on, 2014, pp. 353-357.
- [36] B.W. Boehm, Software Cost Estimation with Cocomo II: Prentice Hall, 2000.
- [37] S.Basri, N. Kama, and R. Ibrahim, "[COCHCOMO: An extension of COCOMO II for Estimating Effort for Requirement Changes during Software Development Phase](#)," 2016.

- [38] Asl and Kama, "[A Change Impact Size Estimation Approach during the Software Development](#)," in 2013 22nd Australian Software Engineering Conference, 2013, pp. 68-77.
- [39] B.Sufyan, K. Nazri, A. Saiful, and H. Faizura, "[Using static and dynamic impact analysis for effort estimation](#)," IET Software, vol. 10, pp. 89-95, 2016.
- [40] N.Kama and F.Azli, "[A Change Impact Analysis Approach for the Software Development Phase](#)," presented at the Proceedings of the 2012 19th Asia-Pacific Software Engineering Conference - Volume 01, 2012.
- [41] N.Kama and F.Azli, "[A Change Impact Analysis Approach for the Software Development Phase](#)," in 2012 19th Asia-Pacific Software Engineering Conference, 2012, pp. 583-592.
- [42] B.W. Boehm, R. Madachy, and B. Steece, Software cost estimation with Cocomo II with Cdrom: Prentice Hall PTR, 2000.
- [43] J.W. Creswell, Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches: Sage publications, 2013.
- [44] R.De Lemos, H. Giese, H. A. Müller, M. Shaw, J. Andersson, M. Litoiu, et al., "[Software engineering for self-adaptive systems: A second research roadmap](#)," in Software Engineering for Self-Adaptive Systems II, ed: Springer, 2013, pp. 1-32.
- [45] C.Wohlin and A. Aurum, "[Towards a decision-making structure for selecting a research design in empirical software engineering](#)," Empirical Software Engineering, vol. 20, pp. 1427-1455, 2015.
- [46] D.Garmus and D. Herron, "Function Point Analysis: Measurement Practices for Successful Software Projects pdf," 2001.
- [47] J.J.Cuadrado-Gallego, P. Rodriguez-Soria, A. Gonzalez, D. Castelo, and S. Hakimuddin, "[Early Functional Size Estimation with IFPUG Unit Modified](#)," in Computer and Information Science (ICIS), 2010 IEEE/ACIS 9th International Conference on, 2010, pp. 729-733.
- [48] Q.S.Management. (2018). Function Point Languages Table. Available: <http://www.qsm.com/resources/function-point-languages-table>
- [49] M.Jorgensen and K. Molokken-Ostvold, "[Reasons for software effort estimation error: impact of respondent role, information collection approach, and data analysis method](#)," IEEE Transactions on Software engineering, vol. 30, pp. 993-1007, 2004.
- [50] V.Nguyen, B.Steece, and B. Boehm, "[A constrained regression technique for COCOMO calibration](#)," in Proceedings of the Second ACM-IEEE international symposium on Empirical software engineering and measurement, 2008, pp. 213-222.

AUTHORS

Jalal Shah, he is pursuing PhD in the field of Software Engineering from Universiti Teknologi Malaysia. He has more than 8 year of teaching & research experience. He is currently working in the area of Software Effort Estimation. He has also published & presented papers in refereed journals and conferences.

Nazri Kama, He is an Associate Professor at Universiti Teknologi Malaysia (UTM) specializing in software engineering. He graduated in Bachelor in Management Information System from Universiti Teknologi Malaysia. Later, he obtained a Master Degree from the same university in Real-time Software Engineering. In 2011, he received a Doctorate in Software Engineering from the University of Western Australia in Australia

Nur Azaliah Abu Bakar, PhD is a Senior Lecturer at Advanced Informatics Department, Razak Faculty of Technology and Informatics, Universiti Teknologi Malaysia. She graduated with a Bachelor (Information Technology) in Information Systems Engineering from Multimedia University (MMU) Malaysia (2000). She then obtained her Masters in Information Technology from Universiti Teknologi Mara (UiTM) in 2004. In 2017 she was awarded a Doctor of Philosophy degree in Information Technology (Enterprise Architecture) by Universiti Teknologi Malaysia

GENERIC MODELLING USING UML EXTENSIONS FOR QUEENS CHALLENGE PUZZLE GAME FROM 1 TO 25 LEVELS SYSTEM

**Hussain Mohammad Abu-Dalbouh, Ghadeer AlJibreen and Nehal
AlDowighri**

**Qassim University, Computer Science Department, College of Sciences and
Arts in Unaizah, Qassim, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia**

ABSTRACT

The Unified Modeling Language (UML) is a language for the specification, visualization, and documentation of object-oriented software systems. Existing UML diagrams can be used to conveniently model behavior, but these diagrams can be hardly used to model games. However, UML cannot describe in an explicit manner the games requirements needed for modeling Queens Challenge Game. In this study, the modeling of queens challenge puzzle from 1 to 25 levels is discussed, the proposed extension to UML covering the use case diagram, sequence diagram, activity diagram and class diagram aspects of proposed at the various views and diagrams of the UML. The use of queens challenge game is illustrated using a queens challenge puzzle from 1 to 25 levels example. The purpose of this section is describing the extensions made in each of the UML diagrams, to allow the explicit representation of the proposed system. First, Context Diagram for proposed N-queen game system is introduced. Then, the proposed modifications to the UML are mentioned. Therefore, this study is aimed to showcase the game analysis, design of concept of game, a precise form of game-level operation specification, and an operation schema declaratively describes the effects of a game operation by using case model, actors, use case, relationships between the actors, the use case, interaction between the prototype and its user, sequence diagram, activity diagram and class diagram of queens challenge puzzle from 1 to 25 levels as defined by the Unified Modeling Language (UML).

KEYWORDS

Diagrams, Game, Queen, Solution, Unified modeling language, System, Analysis

For More Details: <http://aircconline.com/ijsea/V9N6/9618ijsea03.pdf>

Volume Link: <http://www.airccse.org/journal/ijsea/current.html>

REFERENCES

- [1] Wienberg, A., F. Matthes, & M. Boger, (1999) "[Modeling dynamic software components in UML](#)". Proceedings of the 2nd International Conference on the Unified Modeling Language: Beyond the Standard. Fort Collins, CO, USA, October 28-30.
- [2] Booch, G., J. Rumbaugh, & I. Jacobson, (1998) "[The Unified Modeling Language User Guide](#)". 2nd Edn., Addison-Wesley, Reading, MA.
- [3] OMG, (1999) "[OMG Unified Modeling Language Specification](#)", Version 1.3. Published by the OMG Unified Modeling Language Revision Task Force on its WEB site: Retrieved from: <http://uml.shl.com/artifacts.htm>.
- [4] Anastasios G. Bakaoukas, Florin Coadă, Fotis Liarokapis (2016) "[Examining brain activity while playing computer games](#)". J. Multimodal User Interfaces 10(1): 13-29 (2016).
- [5] Bikramijit, B., Peter, S. (2007) "[General game learning using knowledge transfer](#)". In Proceedings of the International Joint Conference on Artificial Intelligence (IJCAI), p 672-677.
- [6] Genesereth, M. R., Love, N., & Pell, B. (2005) "[General Game Playing Overview of the AAI competition](#)". AI Magazine, 26(2), 62-72.
- [7] Hilmar, F., Yngvi, B. (2010) "[Learning simulation control in general game-playing agents](#)". In Proceedings of the AAI Conference on Artificial Intelligence, p 954-959.
- [8] Love, N., Hinrichs, T., & Genesereth, M. (2006, April 4) "[General Game Playing: Game description language specification](#)".
- [9] Genesereth, M. R., Fikes, R. E. (1992) "[Knowledge interchange format, version 3.0 reference manual](#)". Stanford: Technical Report Technical Report Logic 92-1.
- [10] Stefan, E., Peter, K. (2007). Symbolic exploration for general game playing in PDDL. In Workshop on Planning and Games at the International Conference on Automated Planning and Scheduling (ICAPS).

- [11] Abu-Dalbouh, H. (2014) "[m-TOPP-UML: An Extension to UML for the Modeling of Mobile Tracking on Patient Progress System](http://maxwellsci.com/print/rjaset/v7-1388-1394.pdf)". Research Journal of Applied Sciences, Engineering and Technology, Vol. 7, Issue 7, pp: 1202-1208. February 2014. Available: <http://maxwellsci.com/print/rjaset/v7-1388-1394.pdf>
- [12] Jeffrey A., Hoffer, (2011) "[Modern System Analysis and Design](#)", sixth edition, Prentice Hall.
- [13] Rumbaugh, J. and I. Jacobson, (1999)"[The Unified Modeling Language Reference Manual](#)". Addison.
- [14] Oestereich, B., (2001)"[Developing Software with UML: Object-oriented Analysis and Design in Practice](#)". Person Education, London.
- [15] Wesley, Boston. Scott, K., (2001)"UML Explained". Addison-Wesley, Boston, Massachusetts.

INVESTIGATING GAME DEVELOPERS' GUILT EMOTIONS USING SENTIMENT ANALYSIS

Lamiaa Mostafa and Marwa Abd Elghany

**Department of Business Information Systems, College of Management and
Technology, Arab Academy for Science & Technology, Alexandria, Egypt**

ABSTRACT

Game Development is one of the most important emerging fields in software engineering era. Game addiction is the nowadays disease which is combined with playing computer and videogames. Shame is a negative feeling about self evaluation as well as guilt that is considered as a negative evaluation of the transgressing behaviour, both are associated with adaptive and concealing responses. Sentiment analysis demonstrates a huge progression towards the understanding of web users' opinions. In this paper, the sentiments of game developers are examined to measure their guilt's emotions when working in this career. The sentiment analysis model is implemented through the following steps: sentiment collector, sentiment pre-processing, and then machine learning methods were used. The model classifies sentiments into guilt or no guilt and is trained with 1000 Reddit website sentiment. Results have shown that Support Vector Machine (SVM) approach is more accurate in comparison to Naïve Bayes (NB) and Decision Tree.

KEYWORDS

Ethics, Game Addiction, Guilt Emotions, Software Engineering, Sentiment Analysis Model & Value Sensitive Design

For More Details: <http://airconline.com/ijsea/V9N6/9618ijsea04.pdf>

Volume Link: <http://www.airccse.org/journal/ijsea/current.html>

REFERENCES

- [1] R.M.Veatch, (1977), Case Studies in Medical Ethics, Harvard University Press, Cambridge.
- [2] D.L.Schmoldt, H.M. Rauscher, (1994), '[Knowledge management and six supporting technologies](#)', Comput. Electron.Agric., 10 (1), 11–30.
- [3] A.J.Thomson, (1997), '[Artificial Intelligence and environmental ethics](#)', AI Appl., 11 (1), 69–73.
- [4] GerlindWisskirchen et al., (April 2017) '[Artificial Intelligence and Robotics and Their Impact on the Workplace](#)', IBA Global Employment Institute.
- [5] K.Reed, (July/August 2000), "[Software Engineering- A New Millennium?](#)," IEEE Software, pp.107, in D.W. Gotterbarn (a), (1996), Software Engineering: The New Professionalism, The Responsible Software Engineer, ed. Colin Meyer, Springer Verlag.
- [6] R.O.Mason, (1986), '[Four ethical issues of the information age](#)', MIS Q., vol. 10 (1), p. 5–12.
- [7] D.A.Bella, (1992), '[Ethics and the credibility of applied science](#)', in: G.H. Reeves, D.L. Bottom, M.H. Brookes, M.H. (Technical coordinators), Ethical Questions for Resource Managers, USDA Forest Service General Technical Report PNW-GTR-288, pp. 19–32.
- [8] T.Forester, P. Morrison, (1994), Computer Ethics, MIT Press, Cambridge,.
- [9] The joint ACM/IEEE-CS Software Engineering Code was published as: Don Gotterbarn, Keith Miller, and Simon Rogerson,(November 1997), '[Software Engineering Code of Ethics](#)', Communication of the ACM , Vol. 40, Issue 11, pp. 110-118, DOI: 10.1145/265684.265699
- [10] D.Gotterbarn, (2002), SOFTWARE ENGINEERING ETHICS, published by Software Engineering Ethics Research Institute forEncyclopedia of Software Engineering. Availableat: <https://www.uio.no/studier/emner/matnat/ifi/INF3700/v12/undervisningsmateriale/Software%20engineering%20ethics.pdf>
- [11] D.W. Gotterbarn (b),(1996), Establishing Standards of Professional Practice, chapter 3 in The Responsible Software Engineer, ed. Colin Meyer, Springer Verlag.
- [12] SE Code,(October 1999), Computer Society and ACM Approve Software Engineering Code of Ethics, Computer, pages 84-88.

- [13] G.Pour, M. Griss, and M. Lutz, (May 2000), "[The Push to Make Software Engineering Respectable](#)", Computer, page 35-43.
- [14] L.B. West,(October 1991), "[Professional Civil Engineering: Responsibility](#)," Journal of Professional Issues in Engineering Education and Practice, 117, 4.
- [15] D.W. Gotterbarn,(November/December 1999), "[How the new Software Engineering Code of Ethics Affects You](#)", IEEE Software, 58-64.
- [16] Wallach, Wendell og Allen, Colin, (2009), Moral Machines: Teaching Robots Right from Wrong, New York: Oxford University Press.
- [17] Jim Tørresen, (2014), Future Perspectives on Artificial Intelligence (AI), University of Oslo.
- [18] Anderson, Michael og Susan Leigh, (2011), Machine Ethics, Cambridge University Press.
- [19] BATYA FRIEDMAN, PETER H. KAHN, JR., AND ALAN BORNING, (2012), Value Sensitive Design and Information Systems, University of Washington, In P. Zhang & D. Galletta (Eds.), Human-Computer Interaction in Management Information Systems: Foundations, M.E. Sharpe, Inc: NY.
- [20] N.G. LEVESON, (1991), '[Software safety in embedded computer systems](#)', Commun. ACM, Vol. 34, Iss. 2, P. 34-46.
- [21] B.FRIEDMAN, P. H. JR. KAHN, AND J. HAGMAN, (2003), '[Hardware companions?: What online AIBO discussion forums reveal about the human-robotic relationship](#)', Conference Proceedings of CHI 2003, 273- 280, New York, NY: ACM Press.
- [22] P.G. NEUMANN, (1995), Computer Related Risks, New York, NY: Association for Computing Machinery Press.
- [23] E.TURIEL, (1983), The Development of Social Knowledge, Cambridge, England: Cambridge University Press.
- [24] E.TURIEL, (1998), 'Moral development',In N. Eisenberg, Ed., Social, Emotional, and Personality Development, (pp. 863-932), Vol. 3 of W. Damon, Ed., Handbook of Child Psychology, 5th edition, New York, NY: Wiley.
- [25] B.FRIEDMAN, (1997), '[Social judgments and technological innovation: Adolescents, understanding of property, privacy, and electronic information](#)', Computers in Human Behaviour, 13(3), 327-351.

- [26] M.J. HERSKOVITS,(1952), Economic Anthropology: A Study of Comparative Economics, New York, NY: Alfred A. Knopf.
- [27] T.A. LIPINSKI, and J. J. BRITZ, (2000), '[Rethinking the ownership of information in the 21st century: Ethical implications](#)', Ethics and Information Technology, 2, 1, 49-71.
- [28] P.E. AGRE, and M. ROTENBERG, (1998), Eds., '[Technology and Privacy: The New Landscape](#)', MIT Press, Cambridge, MA.
- [29] V.BELLOTTI, (1998), Design for privacy in multimedia computing and communications environments, In P. E. Agre and M. Rotenberg, Eds., Technology and Privacy: The New Landscape (pp. 63-98), Cambridge, MA: The MIT Press.
- [30] M.BOYLE, C. EDWARDS, and S. GREENBERG, (2000), '[The effects of filtered video on awareness and privacy](#)', In Proceedings of Conference on Computer Supported Cooperative Work (CSCW 2000), 1-10, New York, NY: Association for Computing Machinery.
- [31] L.FUCHS, (1999), '[AREA: A cross-application notification service for groupware](#)', In Proceedings of ECSCW 1999, Kluwer, Dordrecht Germany, 61-80.
- [32] G.JANCKE, G. D. VENOLIA, J. GRUDIN, J. J. CADIZ, and A. GUPTA, (2001), 'Linking public spaces: Technical and social issues', In Proceedings of CHI 2001, 530-537.
- [33] L.PALEN, and P. DOURISH, (2003), '[Privacy and trust: Unpacking, privacy, for a networked world](#)', In Proceedings of CHI 2003, 129-136.
- [34] H.NISSENBAUM, (1998), '[Protecting privacy in an information age: The problem with privacy in public](#)', Law and Philosophy, 17, pp. 559-596.
- [35] D.J. PHILLIPS, (1998), Cryptography, secrets, and structuring of trust, In P. E. Agre and M. Rotenberg, Eds., Technology and Privacy: The New Landscape (pp. 243-276), Cambridge, MA: The MIT Press.
- [36] F.D. SCHOEMAN, (1984),Philosophical Dimensions of Privacy: An Anthology, Cambridge, England: Cambridge University Press.
- [37] M.SVENSSON, K. HOOK, J. LAAKSOLAHTI, and A. WAERN, (2001), '[Social navigation of food recipes](#)', In Proceedings of the Conference of Human Factors in Computing Systems (CHI 2001), 341-348, New York, NY: Association for Computing Machinery.

- [38] J. ABERG, and N. SHAHMEHRI, (2001), '[An empirical study of human Web assistants: Implications for user support in Web information systems](#)', In Proceedings of the Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems (CHI 2000), (pp. 404-411), New York, NY: Association for Computing Machinery Press.
- [39] B.SHNEIDERMAN, (1999), '[Universal usability: Pushing human-computer interaction research to empower every citizen](#)', ISR Technical Report 99-72, University of Maryland, Institute for Systems Research, College Park, MD.
- [40] B.SHNEIDERMAN, (2000), 'Universal usability', Commun.of the ACM, 43, 5, 84-91, 2000.
- [41] M.COOPER, and P. REJMER, (2001), '[Case study: Localization of an accessibility evaluation](#)', In Extended Abstracts of the Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems (CHI 2001), 141-142, New York, NY: Association for Computing Machinery Press.
- [42] J.A. JACKO, M. A. DIXON, R. H. JR. ROSA, I. U. SCOTT, and C. J. PAPPAS, (1999), '[Visual profiles: A critical component of universal access](#)', In Proceedings of the Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems (CHI 99), pp. 330-337, New York, NY: Association for Computing Machinery Press.
- [43] C.STEPHANIDIS, (2001),Ed. 2001 User Interfaces for All: Concepts, Methods, and Tools, Mahwah, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates.
- [44] A.BAIER, (1986), Trust and antitrust, Ethics, 231-260.
- [45] L.J. CAMP, (2000), Trust & Risk in Internet Commerce, MIT Press, Cambridge, MA, L. J.
- [46] A.DIEBERGER, K. HOOK, M. SVENSSON, and P. LONNQVIST, (2001), '[Social navigation research agenda](#)', InExtended Abstracts of the Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems (CHI 2001), pp. 107-108, NewYork, NY: Association of Computing Machinery Press.
- [47] F.N. EGGER, (2000) '[Trust me, I am an online vendor.: Towards a model of trust for e-commerce systemdesign](#)', In Extended Abstracts of the Conference of Human Factors in Computing Systems (CHI 2000), 101-102, New York, NY: Association for Computing Machinery.
- [48] B.J. FOGG, and H. TSENG,(1999), '[The elements of computer credibility](#)', In Proceedings of CHI 1999, ACM Press, 80-87.

- [49] B.FRIEDMAN, P. H. JR. KAHN, and D. C. HOWE, (2000), 'Trust online', Commun.ACM, 43, 12, 34-40.
- [50] P.H. JR. KAHN, and E. TURIEL, (1988), '[Children's conceptions of trust in the context of social expectations](#)', Merrill-Palmer Quarterly, 34, 403-419.
- [51] R.C. MAYER, J. H. DAVIS, AND F. D. SCHOORMAN,(1995), '[An integrative model of organizational trust](#)', TheAcademy of Management Review, vol. 20, issue 3, pp. 709-734.
- [52] J.S. OLSON, and G. M. OLSON, (2000), 'i2i trust in e-commerce', Communications of the ACM, 43(12), 41-44.
- [53] H.NISSENBAUM, (2001), '[Securing trust online: Wisdom or oxymoron](#)', Boston University Law Review, 81(3), 635-664.
- [54] E.ROCCO, (1998), '[Trust breaks down in electronic contexts but can be repaired by some initial face-to-face contact](#)', In Proceedings of CHI 1998, ACM Press, 496-502.
- [55] B.FRIEDMAN, and H. NISSENBAUM, (1997), '[Software agents and user autonomy](#)', Proceedings of the FirstInternational Conference on Autonomous Agents, 466-469, New York, NY: Association for Computing Machinery Press.
- [56] T.E. JR. HILL, (1991), Autonomy and self-respect, Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- [57] E.A. ISAACS, J. C. TANG, and T. MORRIS, (1996), '[Piazza: A desktop environment supporting impromptu andplanned interactions](#)', In Proceedings of the Conference on Computer Supported Cooperative Work (CSCW 96), pp. 315-324, New York, NY: Association for Computing Machinery Press.
- [58] L.SUCHMAN, (1994), 'Do categories have politics? The language/action perspective reconsidered', CSCW Journal, vol. 2, no. 3, pp. 177-190.
- [59] T.WINOGRAD, (1994), '[Categories, disciplines, and social coordination](#)', CSCW Journal, vol. 2, no. 3, pp. 191-197.
- [60] R.FADEN, and T. BEAUCHAMP, (1986), A History and Theory of Informed Consent, New York, NY: OxfordUniversity Press.
- [61] B.FRIEDMAN, L. MILLETT, and E. FELTEN, (2000), '[Informed Consent Online: A Conceptual Model and DesignPrinciples](#)', University of Washington Computer Science & Engineering Technical Report 00-12-2.

- [62] The Belmont Report: Ethical Principles and Guidelines for the Protection of Human Subjects of Research, The National Commission for the Protection of Human Subjects of Biomedical and Behavioural Research, 1978.
- [63] B.FRIEDMAN, and P. H. JR. KAHN, (1992), '[Human agency and responsible computing: Implications for computer system design](#)', Journal of Systems Software, 17, 7-14.
- [64] B.FRIEDMAN, and L. MILLETT, (1995), '[It's the computer's fault: Reasoning about computers as moral agents](#)', In Conference Companion of the Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems (CHI 95), (pp. 226-227), New York, NY: Association for Computing Machinery Press.
- [65] B.REEVES, and C. NASS, (1996), The Media Equation: How People Treat Computers, Television, and New Media Like Real People and Places', New York, NY and Stanford, CA: Cambridge University Press and CSLI Publications.
- [66] W.J. BENNETT, and E. J. DELATREE, (1978), '[Moral education in the schools](#)', The Public Interest, 50, pp. 81-98.
- [67] E.A. WYNNE, and K. RYAN, (1993), Reclaiming our schools: A handbook on teaching character, academics, and discipline, New York, Macmillan.
- [68] M.U. BERS, J. GONZALEZ-HEYDRICH, and D. R. DEMASO, (2001), '[Identity construction environments: Supporting a virtual therapeutic community of pediatric patients undergoing dialysis](#)', In Proceedings of the Conference of Human Factors in Computing Systems (CHI 2001), 380-387, New York, NY: Association for Computing Machinery.
- [69] S.ROSENBERG, (1997), Multiplicity of selves, In R. D. Ashmore and L. Jussim, Eds., Self and Identity:Fundamental Issues, (pp. 23-45), New York, NY: Oxford University Press.
- [70] D.J. SCHIANO, and S. WHITE, (1998), '[The first noble truth of cyberspace: People are people \(even when they MOO\)](#)', In Proceedings of the Conference of Human Factors in Computing Systems (CHI 98), 352-359, New York, NY: Association for Computing Machinery.
- [71] S.TURKLE, (1996), '[Life on the Screen: Identify in the Age of the Internet](#)', New York, NY: Simon and Schuster.
- [72] B.FRIEDMAN, and P. H. JR. KAHN, Human values, ethics, and design, In J. Jacko and A. Sears, Eds., The Human-Computer Interaction Handbook, Lawrence Erlbaum Associates, Mahwah NJ, 2003.

- [73] M.WEISER, and J. S. BROWN, (1997), The coming age of calm technology, In P. Denning and B. Metcalfe, Eds., *Beyond Calculation: The Next 50 Years of Computing*, (pp. 75-85), New York, NY: Springer-Verlag.
- [74] UNITED NATIONS (2002), Report of the United Nations Conference on Environment and Development, held in Rio de Janeiro, Brazil, 1992. Available from: <http://www.un.org/esa/sustdev/documents/agenda21/english/agenda21toc.html>
- [75] WORLD COMMISSION ON ENVIRONMENT AND DEVELOPMENT (Gro Harlem Brundtland, Chair), *Our Common Future*, Oxford University Press, Oxford, 1987.
- [76] M.HART, (1999), *Guide to Sustainable Community Indicators*, Hart Environmental Data, PO Box 361, North Andover, MA 01845, second edition.
- [77] B. MOLDAN, S. BILLHARZ, and R. MATRAVERS, (1997), *Sustainability Indicators: A Report on the Project on Indicators of Sustainable Development*, Wiley, Chichester, England.
- [78] NORTHWEST ENVIRONMENT WATCH, *This Place on Earth 2002: Measuring What Matters*, Northwest Environment Watch, 1402 Third Avenue, Seattle, WA 98101.
- [79] American Medical Association, AMA takes action on video games, Retrieved October 15, 2007, from <http://www.amaassn.org/ama/pub/category/17770.html>
- [80] M.Griffiths, & R. Wood, (2000), '[Risk factors in adolescence: The case of gambling, videogame playing, and the internet](#)', *Journal of Gambling Studies*, vol. 16, pp. 199–225.
- [81] M.D. Griffiths, M. N. O. Davies, & D. Chappell, (2004), '[Online computer gaming: A comparison of adolescent and adult gamers](#)', *Journal of Adolescence*, vol. 27, pp. 87–96.
- [82] J.P. Charlton, & I. D. W. Danforth, (2007), '[Distinguishing addiction and high engagement in the context of online game playing](#)', *Computers in Human Behavior*, vol. 23, pp. 1531–1548.
- [83] S.Chiu, J. Lee, & D. Huang, (2004), '[Video game addiction in children and teenagers in Taiwan](#)', *Cyber Psychology & Behaviour*, vol. 7, pp. 571–581.
- [84] T.Chou, & C. Ting, (2003), '[The role of flow in cyber-game addiction](#)', *Cyber Psychology & Behaviour*, vol. 6, pp. 663–675.
- [85] S.E. Fisher, (1994), '[Identifying video game addiction in children and adolescents](#)', *Addictive Behaviours*, vol. 19, pp. 545–553.

- [86] M.D. Griffiths, & M. N. O. Davies, (2005), Videogame addiction: Does it exist?, In J. Goldstein & J. Raessens (Eds.), Handbook of computer game studies (pp. 359–368). Boston: MIT Press.
- [87] S.M. Grüsser, C. Thalemann, & M. Griffiths, (2007), '[Excessive computer game playing: Evidence for addiction and aggression?](#)', Cyber Psychology & Behaviour, vol. 10, pp. 290–292.
- [88] M.R. Hauge, & D. A. Gentile, (April 2003), '[Video game addiction among adolescents: Associations with academic performance and aggression](#)', Paper presented at Society for Research in Child Development Conference, Tampa, FL.
- [89] C.Ko, J. Yen, C. Chen, S. Chen, & C. Yen, (2005), '[Gender differences and related factors affecting online gaming addiction among Taiwanese adolescents](#)', Journal of Nervous and Mental Disease, vol.193, pp. 273–277.
- [90] B.D. Ng, & P. Wiemer-Hastings, (2005), '[Addiction to the internet and online gaming](#)', Cyber Psychology & Behaviour, vol. 8, pp. 110–113.
- [91] W.B. Soper, & M. J. Miller, (1983), '[Junk-time junkies: An emerging addiction among students](#)', The School Counselor, 31, 40–43.
- [92] C.S. Wan, & W. B. Chiou, (2006), '[Psychological motives and online games addiction: A test of flow theory and humanistic needs theory for Taiwanese adolescents](#)', Cyber Psychology & Behaviour, vol. 9, pp. 317–324.
- [93] R.A. T. Salguero, & R. M. B. Moran, (2002), '[Measuring problem video game playing in adolescents](#)', Addiction, 97, 1601–1606.
- [94] A.F. Seay, & R. E. Kraut, (2007), '[Project massive: Self-regulation and problematic use of online gaming](#)', In CHI 2007: Proceedings of the ACM conference on human factors in computing systems, (pp. 829–838). New York: ACM Press.
- [95] A.Johansson, & K. G. Gotestam, (2004), '[Problems with computer games without monetary reward: Similarity to pathological gambling](#)', Psychological Reports, 95, 641–650.
- [96] G.A. Keepers, '[Pathological preoccupation with video games](#)', Journal of the American Academy of Child & Adolescent Psychiatry, 29, 49–50, (1990).
- [97] M.Griffiths, (2005), '[A “components” model of addiction within a biopsychosocial framework](#)', Journal of Substance Use, vol. 10, pp. 191–197.
- [98] J.Mendelson, & N. Mello, (1986), The addictive personality, New York: Chelsea House.

- [99] Knime.com [Internet].Knime; [cited 2018 Nov 11]. Available from: <http://www.knime.com/>
- [100] M. El-Masri, N. Altrabsheh, H. Mansour, A. Ramsay, (November 2017), ‘[A web-based tool for Arabic sentiment analysis](#)’, 3rd International Conference on Arabic Computational Linguistics ACLing 2017, 5–6, Dubai, United Arab Emirates.
- [101] PorterStemmer [Internet]. PorterStemmer; [cited 2018 Nov 11]. Available from: <https://tartarus.org/martin/PorterStemmer/>
- [102] J.Ramos, (2003),‘[Using tf-idf to determine word relevance in document queries](#)’, In First International Conference on Machine Learning, New Brunswick:NJ, USA, Rutgers University.
- [103] Y.Zhang, R. Jin, &ZH.Zhou, (December 2010),‘[Understanding bag-of-words model: AStatistical Framework](#),[International Journal of Machine Learning and Cybernetics](#), Volume 1, Issue 1–4, pp. 43–52.
- [104] M.Araujo, P.Goncalves, M. Cha, F.Benevenuto, (2014),‘[I feel: a system that compares and combines sentiment analysis methods](#)’, in: Proceedings of the 23rd International Conference on World Wide Web, ACM. pp. 75–78
- [105] N.Altrabsheh, M.Cocca, S.Fallahkhair, (2015), ‘[Predicting students emotions using machine learning techniques](#)’, in: The 17th International Conference on Artificial Intelligence in Education.
- [106] A.Go, R. Bhayani, L.Huang, (2009),Twitter sentiment classification using distant supervision, CS224N Project Report, Stanford.
- [107] R.Duwairi, M. El-Orfali, (2014),‘[A study of the effects of preprocessing strategies on sentiment analysis for arabic text](#)’,Journal of Information Science, 40, 501–513.
- [108] B Pang, L. Lee, (2004), ‘[A sentimental education: Sentiment analysis using subjectivity summarization based on minimum cuts](#)’, Annual Meeting on Association for Computational Linguistics, 42, 271–278.
- [109] D.Hand, (2012), ‘[Assessing the Performance of Classification Methods](#)’,International Statistical Review, 80, 3, 400–414.
- [110] L.Mostafa,M. Farouk, and M. Fakhry, (2009),‘[An automated approach for webpage classification](#)’, ICCTA09 Proceedings of 19th International conference on computer theory and applications,Vol. 5, Issue 10,pp. 10-15.

- [111] Reddit [Internet]. Reddit; [cited 2018 Nov 12]. Available from: <https://www.reddit.com/>
- [112] D.Lewis, and J. Catlett, (10-13 July 1994), '[Heterogeneous Uncertainty Sampling for Supervised Learning](#)', Proceedings of the Eleventh International Conference, Rutgers University, New Brunswick, NJ.
- [113] H.B. Lewis, (1971), Shame and guilt in neurosis, New York, NY: International Universities Press.
- [114] J.P. Tangney, (1991), '[Moral affect: The good, the bad, and the ugly](#)', Journal of Personality and Social Psychology, 61, 598- 607. doi:10.1037/0022-3514.61.4.598
- [115] S.T. Wolf, T. R. Cohen, A. T. Panter, & C. A. Insko, (2010), '[Shame proneness and guilt proneness: Toward the further understanding of reactions to public and private transgressions](#)', Self and Identity, 9, 337-362. doi:10.1080/15298860903106843
- [116] S. Roos, E. V. E. Hodges, & C. Salmivalli, (2014), '[Do guilt and shame-proneness differentially predict prosocial, aggressive, and withdrawn behaviors during early adolescence?](#)', Developmental Psychology, 50, 941-946. doi:10.1037/a0033904
- [117] F. Calefato, F. Lanubile, F. Maiorano, N. Novielli, (2018), '[Sentiment Polarity Detection for Software Development](#)', Empir Software Eng (2018), 23: 1352.
- [118] B. Rajat S. Gaonkar, (2017), '[Sentiment Analysis of Product Reviews using Hadoop](#)', IJSRD – International Journal for Scientific Research Development, Vol. 4, Issue 12.
- [119] X. Lei, X. Qian, (2015), '[Rating Prediction via Exploring Service Reputation](#)', IEEE 17th International Workshop on Multimedia Signal processing.
- [120] D. Das, S. Sharma, S. Natani, N. Khare, and B. Singh, (2017), '[Sentimental Analysis for Airline Twitter data](#)', IOP Conf. Series: Materials Science and Engineering, 263, 042067.
- [121] W. Mariel, S. Mariyah, and S. Pramana, (2018), '[Sentiment analysis: a comparison of deep learning neural network algorithm with SVM and naïve Bayes for Indonesian text](#)' IOP Conf. Series: Journal of Physics: Conf. Series 971, 012049.

SECURING SOFTWARE DEVELOPMENT STAGES USING ASPECT-ORIENTATION CONCEPTS

Aws A. Magableh and Anas M. R. AlSobeh

**Department of Computer Information Systems
Faculty of Computer Science and Information Technology
Yarmouk University, Irbid, Jordan**

ABSTRACT

In the past 10 years, the research community has produced a significant number of design notations to represent security properties and concepts in a design artifact. The need to improve the security of software has become a key issue for developers. The security function needs to be incorporated into the software development process at the requirement, analysis, design, and implementation stages as doing so may help to smooth integration and to protect systems from attack. Security affects all aspects of a software program, which makes the incorporation of security features a crosscutting concern. Therefore, this paper looks at the feasibility and potential advantages of employing an aspect orientation approach in the software development lifecycle to ensure efficient integration of security. These notations are aimed at documenting and analyzing security in a software design model. It also proposes a model called the Aspect-Oriented Software Security Development Life Cycle (AOSSDLC), which covers arrangement of security activities and deliverables for each development stage. It is concluded that aspect orientation is one of the best options available for installing security features not least because of the benefit that no changes need to be made to the existing software structure.

KEYWORDS

Aspect Orientation, AO, Aspect-Oriented Programming, AOP, SSDL, Software Security Development Life Cycle, Security, Notation, Software Design.

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Volume Link: <http://www.airccse.org/journal/ijsea/current.html>

REFERENCES

- [1] Microsoft. Microsoft security intelligence report: July-December 2016. <http://www.microsoft.com/technet/security/default.mspix>, 2016
- [2] Http://msdn.microsoft.com/en-us/library/ms995349.aspx#sdl2_topic1_1, retrieved July 2017
- [3] Selecting a Development Approach, Retrieved May 2017.
- [4] Ebse, B. & Charters, S. 2007. Guidelines for Performing Systematic Literature Reviews in Software Engineering.
- [5] Maryati, Y. 2011. Systematic Review Hand-on Workshop. Research Center of Software Technology and management, Faculty of information and Technology, UKM.
- [6] Howard, M., & Lipner, S. (2006). The security development life cycle (Vol. 8). Redmond: Microsoft Press.
- [7] Sasikala D, The Most Common Methodologies for Secure Software Development, International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Development, Volume 3; Issue 3; March 2016; Page No. 194-197
- [8] Muhammad Asad, Shafique Ahmed, Model Driven Architecture for Secure Software Development Life Cycle, International Journal of Computer Science and Information Security (IJCSIS), Vol. 14, No. 6, June 2016
- [9] Zhendong Ma, Christian Wagner, Arndt Bonitz, and Thomas Bleier , Model-driven Secure Development Life cycle, International Journal of Security and Its Applications Vol. 6 No. 2, April, 2012
- [10] Microsoft, Security Development Life cycle SDL Process Guidance Version 5.2, May23, 2012
- [11] F. Truyen, "[The Fast Guide to Model Driven Architecture; The Basics of Model Driven Architecture](#)," Cephass Consulting Corp , 2006
- [12] Eoin Keary, Jim Manico, "[Secure Development Life cycle](#)," in OWASP, Hamburg
- [13] Richard Kissel, Kevin Stine , Matthew Scholl , Hart Rossman , Jim Fahlsing , Jessica Gulick, "[Security Considerations in the System Development Life Cycle](#)," National Institute of Standards and Technology , Gaithersburg, 2008 .
- [14] Bart De Win , Riccardo Scandariato, Koen Buyens, Johan Gre´goire, Wouter Joosen, On the secure software development process: CLASP, SDL and Touchpoints compared, Information and Software Technology 51 (2009) 1152–1171

- [15] Georg, G., Ray, I., and France, R., "[Using Aspects to Design a Secure System](#)", In Proc. 8th IEEE Int'l Conf. on Eng. of Complex Computer Systems (ICECCS'02), pp. 117-128, 2002.
- [16] Shah, V. and F. Hill, "[An Aspect-Oriented Framework](#)", In Proc. DARPA Info.Survivability Conf. and Exposition (DISCEX'03), pp. 22-24, 2003.
- [17] Yu, H. et.al., "[Secure Software Architectures Design by Aspect Orientation](#)", In Proc. 10th Int'l Conf. on Eng. of Complex Computer Sys (ICECCS'05), pp. 45-57, 2005.
- [18] Viega, J., Bloch, J.T., and P. Chandra, "[Applying Aspect Oriented Programming to Security](#)", In Cutter IT Journal, 14(2):31-31, 2001.
- [19] Symatec, Internet Security Threat Report, Volume 21, April 2016
- [20] Cisco, Cisco Annual Cybersecurity Report 2017 Infographic
- [21] Schwanninger, C., & Joosen, W. (2011). Transactions on Aspect-Oriented Software Development VIII (Vol. 6580). S. Katz, & M. Mezini (Eds.). Springer Science & Business Media.
- [22] Smith, B. (2015). Object-Oriented Programming. In Advanced ActionScript 3(pp. 1-23). Apress.
- [23] Avison, D., & Fitzgerald, G. (2003). Information systems development: methodologies, techniques and tools. McGraw Hill.
- [24] Magableh, A., Shukur, Z., & Ali, N. M. (2013). Aspectual UML approach to support AspectJ
- [25] Filman, R., Elrad, T., Clarke, S., & Akşit, M. (2004). Aspect-oriented software development. Addison-Wesley Professional.
- [26] Groher, I., & Voelter, M. (2007, March). XWeave: models and aspects in concert. In Proceedings of the 10th international workshop on Aspect-oriented modeling (pp. 35-40).ACM.
- [27] De B. Win, B. Vanhaute, B. De Decker, "[Security through Aspect-Oriented Programming](#)", Advances in Network and Distributed Systems Security, pp. 125-138, 2001.
- [28] Dehlinger J. and N. V. Subramanian. Architecting Secure Software Systems Using an Aspect-Oriented Approach: A Survey of Current Research. Technical report, Iowa State University, 2006
- [29] De Win, Bart, Wouter Joosen, and Frank Piessens. "[Developing secure applications through aspect-oriented programming.](#)" Aspect-Oriented Software Development (2005): 633-650.
- [30] Marchand de Kerchove, F., Noyé, J., & Südholt, M. (2013, March). Aspectizing javascript security. In Proceedings of the 3rd workshop on Modularity in systems software (pp. 7-12).ACM.

- [31] Safonov, V. O. (2008). Using aspect-oriented programming for trustworthy software development (Vol. 5). John Wiley & Sons.
- [32] Mourad, A., Laverdière, M. A., & Debbabi, M. (2008). [An aspect-oriented approach for the systematic security hardening of code](#). *computers & security*, 27(3), 101-11
- [33] Mouheb, D., Talhi, C., Nouh, M., Lima, V., Debbabi, M., Wang, L., Pourzandi, M.: Aspect-Oriented Modeling for Representing and Integrating Security Concerns in UML. In: R.Y. Lee, O. Ormandjieva, A. Abran, C. Constantinides (eds.) Proceedings of the ACIS Conference on Software Engineering Research, Management, and Applications, Studies in Computational Intelligence, vol. 296, pp. 197–213. Springer (2010)
- [34] A. van den Berghe, R. Scandariato, K. Yskout, W. Joosen, "[Design notations for secure software: a systematic literature review](#)", *Software & Systems Modeling*, 2015.
- [35] Keller, F., Wendt, S.: FMC: [An approach towards architecture centric system development](#). In: Proceedings of 10th IEEE International Conference and Workshop on the Engineering of Computer-Based Systems, 2003, pp. 173–182. IEEE (2003)
- [36] Matulevičius, R., Dumas, M.: A Comparison of Secure UML and UML sec for Role-Based Access Control. In: *Databases and Information Systems*, pp. 171–185 (2010)

EMPIRICALLY VALIDATED SIMPLICITY EVALUATION MODEL FOR OBJECT ORIENTED SOFTWARE

Dr. Abdullah¹ and Dr. Mahfuzul Huda²

¹Assistant Professor, Adigrat University, Adigrat- Tigray, Ethiopia-Africa.

²Assistant Professor, Saudi Electronic University, Riyadh -Saudi Arabia.

ABSTRACT

Software program developers need to go from beginning to ending and understand source code of the program and other software attributes. The software complexities and length of the program exceedingly affects many design level quality attributes, specifically Simplicity, Testability and software Maintainability. Incomplete design of any software generally leads to misunderstanding and ambiguities and therefore to gives faulty design and development results. This is mainly seeming and appears owing to the absence of it's an appropriate observation, design and development control. However, high level design and program simplicity are very necessary and one of the vital attributes of the system development cycle. This research paper highlights the impact and significance of design level software simplicity in common and as a one of the most useful key factor or index of software quality assurance and testing. In this research work principally there are three major efforts are made. As a first contribution, a valuable relationship between software design quality factor simplicity and related object oriented design properties, this has been set up. In the second contribution, using design level corresponding metrics a simplicity evaluation model for object oriented software is developed. Subsequently, the developed simplicity model has been rationally authenticated by means of experimental data try-out.

KEYWORDS

Simplicity, Reliability, Maintainability, Testability, Portability, Flexibility, Object Oriented Software.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Boehm BW, Brow JR, Lipow M, McLeod G, Merritt M. Characteristics of software quality. North Holland Publishing. Amsterdam, the Netherlands; 1978.
- [2] Abdullah, Dr, M. H. Khan, and Reena Srivastava. "[Flexibility: A Key Factor To Testability](#)", International Journal of Software Engineering & Applications (IJSEA), Vol.6, No.1, January 2015. DOI: 10.5121/ijsea.2015.6108.
- [3] McCall JA, Richards PK, Walters GF. Factors in software quality, RADC TR-77-369: 1977. (Rome: Rome Air Development Center)
- [4] Huda, M., Arya, Y.D.S. and Khan, M.H. (2015) [Evaluating Effectiveness Factor of Object Oriented Design: A Testability Perspective](#). International Journal of Software Engineering & Applications (IJSEA), 6, 41-49. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5121/ijsea.2015.6104>
- [5] Huda, M., Arya, Y.D.S. and Khan, M.H. (2015) Metric Based Testability Estimation Model for Object Oriented Design: Quality Perspective. Journal of Software Engineering and Applications, 8, 234-243. <http://dx.doi.org/10.4236/jsea.2015.84024>
- [6] Abdullah, Dr, Reena Srivastava, and M. H. Khan. "[Testability Measurement Framework: Design Phase Perspective](#)". International Journal of Advanced Research in Computer and Communication Engineering, Vol. 3, Issue 11, Pages 8573- 8576 November 2014.
- [7] Boehm BW, Brown JR, Lipow M. Quantitative evaluation of software quality, In Proceeding of the 2nd International Conference on Software engineering. 1976;592605.
- [8] Abdullah, Dr, M. H. Khan, and Reena Srivastava. "[Testability Measurement Model for Object Oriented Design \(TMMOOD\)](#)". International Journal of Computer Science & Information Technology (IJCSIT), Vol. 7, No 1, February 2015, DOI: 10.5121/ijcsit.2015.7115.
- [9] Grady, RB. Practical software metrics for project management and process improvement, Prentice Hall; 1992.
- [10] Huda, M., Arya, Y.D.S. and Khan, M.H. (2015) Quantifying Reusability of Object Oriented Design: A Testability Perspective. Journal of Software Engineering and Applications, 8, 175-183. <http://dx.doi.org/10.4236/jsea.2015.84018>
- [11] Abdullah, Dr, Reena Srivastava, and M. H. Khan. "[Modifiability: A Key Factor To Testability](#)", International Journal of Advanced Information Science and Technology, Vol. 26, No.26, Pages 62-71 June 2014.
- [12] Dromey RG. Concerning the Chimera (software quality). IEEE Software. 1996;1:3343.

- [13] Jacobson I, Booch G, Rumbaugh J. The unified software development process, Addison Wesley; 1999.
- [14] Drown DJ, Khoshgoftaar TM, Seiya N. Evaluation any sampling and software quality model of high assurance systems, IEEE Transaction on systems, Man and Cybernetics, Part A: Systems and Human. 2009;39(5):1097-1107.
- [15] Abdullah, Dr, Reena Srivastava, and M. H. Khan. "[Testability Estimation of Object Oriented Design: A Revisit](#)". International Journal of Advanced Research in Computer and Communication Engineering, Vol. 2, Issue 8, pages 3086-3090, August 2013.
- [16] Tomar AB, Thakare VM. A systematic study of software quality models, International Journal of software engineering & application. 2011;12(4):61-70.
- [17] ISO 9001:2005, Quality management system Fundamentals and vocabulary; 2005.
- [18] Huda, M., Arya, Y.D.S. and Khan, M.H. (2014) Measuring Testability of Object Oriented Design: A Systematic Review. International Journal of Scientific Engineering and Technology (IJSET), 3, 1313-1319.
- [19] ISO 9001:2001, Quality management system Requirements; 2001.
- [20] ISO /IEC25010: Software engineering– system and software quality requirement and evaluation (SQuaRE)- system and software quality model; 2011.
- [21] Huda, M., Arya, Y.D.S. and Khan, M.H. (2015) [Testability Quantification Framework of Object Oriented Software: A New Perspective](#). International Journal of Advanced Research in Computer and Communication Engineering, 4, 298- 302. <http://dx.doi.org/10.17148/IJARCCE.2015.4168>
- [22] McCable TJ. A complexity measure, IEEE Transaction on Software Engineering, 1976; SE-2(4):308-320.
- [23] Kemerer CF. [An empirical validation of software code estimation models, Communications of the ACM](#). 2008;30(5):416-429.
- [22] Basili VR, Weiss DM. A methodology for collecting valid software engineering data, IEEE Transactions on Software Engineering. 1984;SE-10:728-738.
- [25] Pandian CR. Software metrics – A guide to planning, Analysis, and Application, CRC press Company; 2004.
- [26] MoboDexter Software India Pvt. Ltd., Novel Tech Park, Third Floor, #43/4, GB playa, Hosur Road Bangalore
- [27] Tomar AB, Thakare VM. A systematic study of software quality models, International Journal of software engineering & application. 2011;12(4):61-70.

- [28] Boehm BW, Brow JR, Lipow M, McLeod G, Merritt M. Characteristics of software quality. North Holland Publishing. Amsterdam, the Netherlands; 1978.
- [29] Dromey RG. [A model for software product quality.](#) IEEE Transaction on Software Engineering. 1995;21:146-162.
- [30] ISO /IEC25010: Software engineering– system and software quality requirement and evaluation (SQuaRE)- system and software quality model; 2011.
- [31] Lee, Ming-Chang. "[Software Quality Factors and Software Quality Metrics to Enhance Software Quality Assurance.](#)" British Journal of Applied Science & Technology 4.21 (2014).

AUTHORS

Dr. Abdullah, Assistant Professor, Department of Information Technology, Adigrat University, Ethiopia (Africa). Dr. Abdullah did MCA from UP Technical University & Ph.D. (Computer Applications) from BBD University, Lucknow India. He has more than Twelve Years of Teaching and Research experience as an Associate Professor / Assistant Professor/ Lecturer in reputed Universities of India and Foreign/Abroad. Dr. Abdullah has written Three Books and sixteen study materials for different Indian Government and Private Universities published numerous articles, several research papers in the National and International refereed Journals and conference proceedings. His published research work cited and accepted by lot of academicians and researchers across the world and published research papers got 76 Google Scholar citations. His areas of expertise are Software Quality Assurance, Software Testing, Object Oriented Design and Development. He has around Twelve Years of Teaching and Research experience in India and Abroad. He has contributed a lot in academics & research in the form of delivering lectures, research supervision and curriculum developments. He has also organized Seminars, National & International Conferences. He is a Reviewer and Editorial Board member of various national and International research journals as well as professional bodies.

Dr. Mahfuzul Huda currently working as Assistant Professor in the department of Computer Science & Engineering, Saudi Electronic University, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. He has more than ten years of core teaching experience. Dr. Huda has credible contribution in research work. His research papers accepted and appreciated by various researchers across the world and his published research papers got 66 Google Scholar citations with h-index: 5 & i10-index: 3, in a very short span of time. Subsequently, he has guided more than 50 students for academic projects and seminars and attended more than 30 seminars and workshops related to academic work.

